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Corrosion performance and nanomechanical properties of polylactic acid coatings on WE43 magnesium alloy

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Biodegradable metallic implants are promising biomedical materials to eliminate the problem of repeated surgical interventions. In particular, magnesium is one of the best materials for the manufacture of biodegradable implants. Biodegradation of Mg proceeds with a high rate in biological media, which limits their commercialization. Surface modification of Mg and its alloys is widely used to form functional coatings for various purposes. Organic coatings, mainly natural polymers, provide flexibility in terms of chemical functionalization of the metal surface to mimic the multi-functional performance of the natural bone.

The Mg alloy WE43 is a promising candidate for biomedical applications and examination of its corrosion in different biologically relevant media is of great importance. Moreover, examination nanomechanical properties of such coatings are of great significance for their application. The aim of this work was to investigate the physicochemical properties of organic PLA coatings, their nanomechanical properties and corrosion degradation in Hank's solution through immersion and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) tests.

The microstructure of the WE43 magnesium alloy consists of micrometer-sized Mg–Nd–Y-type IMPs distributed in the α -Mg matrix. Scanning Kelvin probe force microscopy and intermodulation electrostatic force microscopy measurements confirmed high local electrochemical activity of these IMPs. Deposition of the PLA layer on the surface of the WE43 alloy was performed by the immersion method and resulted in the formation of a uniform polymer coating with a surface roughness less than 10 nm. The corrosion rate of the as-treated WE43 alloy in Hank's solution decreased by a factor of 100. Advanced nanomechanical characterization was performed by using multifrequency Intermodulation AFM (ImAFM) providing unique information on conservative and dissipation interaction energy components.

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